

THE IMPACT OF NEGATIVE THINKING AND GRATITUDE ON DEPRESSION AMONG YOUNG ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

Negative thinking may have adverse effects on the state of mind, causing more stress issues, lower self-esteem, and an augmented chance of depression. By practicing gratitude, people might be able to get better mental health conditions. The objective of present study was to examine the relationship among negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. The quantitative research was conducted on negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. Data was collected by using convenient sampling technique. The sample (N= 200) adults of age above 18 were recruited from different universities of the Lahore, Pakistan. Assessment tools employed in this study includes: Automatic thoughts questionnaire- Believability (ATQ-B), The Gratitude Questionnaire-Six Item Form (GQ-6), Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9). Data Analysis was conducted through SPSS (version 23), analysis includes; Descriptive Statistics, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, Linear Regression Analysis and Independent Samples. Findings of the study indicated that there is a significant relationship among Negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. It also revealed that negative thinking, gratefulness and depression equally effect on each other. Furthermore, Depression is a significant predictor to develop negative thinking among adults. It also indicated that the ratio of gratefulness become the cause of less severity in depression symptoms. The findings support mental health professionals, educators, and policy makers in developing gratitude-centered awareness campaigns, school programs, or therapy modules. Ultimately, this research contributes not only to academic literature but also to the practical improvement of psychological health in Pakistani society.

Keywords: Gratitude, Depression, Mental health, negative thinking, adults, university student.

INTRODUCTION

According to the recent analysis, it has been indicated that approximately 3.8 percent of the

world population have depression symptoms (World Health Organization, 2025), and the prevalence

among the adult has been estimated to be 5% and approximately 4% of men and 6% of women are affected world widely (WHO, 2025). Moreover, 5.7 percent of adults, aged more than 60, have depressive symptoms (Terlizzi, 2020). Another study indicated that the diagnosed prevalence ratio is estimated at 280 million people globally, and symptoms severity is approximately 50 percent more prevalent in women than men (Ortega M.A, 2022). More than 10 percent of pregnant women and those who just gave birth are also affected by depression (Benedetti et al., 2022). Worryingly, the number of those dying as a result of suicide has surpassed 700,000 annually, grouped as the fourth leading cause of death among the individuals between the age of 15 and 29 years (Kara & Gulbahce, 2024; WHO, 2025). In one of the study conducted in Karachi, Pakistan indicated that (51%) patients have suffered from depression and (20%) from anxiety in a small group of sample (Hussain et al., 2025).

Depressed patients had significantly low quality of life, absence of social support, and felt stressful (Junaid et al., 2021). One of the most crucial depression predictors remains negative thinking, which is frequently associated with worsening of its symptoms due to the application of maladjusted cognitive processes (Zetsche et al., 2020). Aaron Beck, a US psychiatrist, recognized that there were specific patterns to negative thinking. These patterns are called Cognitive Distortions or Distorted Thinking and these cognitive distortions negatively impact emotional health (Durand, 2015; Hossain, 2025). Conversely, gratitude is tied to symptoms of depression and a better psychological condition (Jans-Beken & Wong, 2021). A study established that gratitude had negative relations to depressive symptoms, indicated that gratitude might be associated with depressive symptoms through satisfaction of the basic psychological needs (James, et al., 2025).

In a Meta analysis, it has been indicated that gratitude works as a protective factor of depressive symptoms (Iodice, et al., 2021). Another research was conducted in china to determine the relation between gratitude and depression, revealed some psychological processes through which gratitude guard against depressed feelings (Liang et al., 2020). Furthermore, the relation between gratitude and

cognitive functioning enhanced the healthy cognitive performance (Kobayashi et al., 2022). Among depression patients chronic illnesses and its finding indicates that higher the gratitude practice decrease the depression symptoms (Cregg & Cheavens, 2021).

Thus, both gratitude and depression have indirectly related with each other (Vandeventer et al., 2024). To further explore this into the current study and in the perspective of Pakistan, the aim of the current study is to explore the relationship between negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults.

The Significance of Study

Mental health concerns, particularly depression, are on the rise in Pakistan, yet they remain under-discussed due to social stigma and limited access to psychological care. Among the many cognitive factors linked to depression, negative thinking patterns play a critical role in worsening emotional distress and hopelessness. This study seeks to explore how gratitude, a positive psychological trait, can potentially buffer the harmful effects of negative thinking and reduce depressive symptoms. By understanding this relationship, the research highlights a powerful yet often overlooked emotional strength that could be cultivated through simple, culturally appropriate interventions.

In a country like Pakistan, where financial, familial, and societal pressures are high, identifying low-cost and effective mental health strategies is essential. Gratitude-based practices may offer a realistic and sustainable approach for promoting resilience and emotional well-being, especially among young people, students, or vulnerable populations. The study's findings support mental health professionals, educators, and policy makers in developing gratitude-centered awareness campaigns, school programs, or therapy modules. Ultimately, this research contributes not only to academic literature but also to the practical improvement of psychological health in Pakistani society

Methodology

The present research was conducted to study the relationship among negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. The current study employs a Correlational research design to investigate the relationship among negative thinking, gratitude and

depression among adults in Lahore, Pakistan. A quantitative approach was selected to conduct the current study as it indicates the reliability and better understanding about the relationship among variables in a certain population group. The sample was selected as N=200 male and female students from different universities of the Lahore. Non-probability convenient sampling strategy was used to recruit the participants. The target population was reached using simple random sampling methods that eliminate prejudice and give each member an equal chance. Participants' selection criteria demanded that students should be, age 18 years and above, studying in university level, and provided, voluntary consent to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

The following criteria have been followed to recruit the participants;

- Aged 18 or above years old
- Who can read and understand Urdu and English
- Who showed willingness to provide the informed consent
- Should be studying any semester of the bachelor level
- Individuals residing in Pakistan at the time of the data collection

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals with cognitive impairments or intellectual disabilities that may affect their ability to understand or complete the questionnaire.
- Those who refuse to provide informed consent or are unwilling to participate voluntarily.
- Participants who have incomplete or inconsistent responses in the assessment tools.
- Individuals with any type of Physical Disability were excluded.

Measures

The Demographic sheet was used to gather personal information. It included age, gender, education level, no of siblings, birth order, father age, father's income, family, environment, occupation, monthly income, residential background, family system, father's occupation, mother's occupation, marital status.

- **Automatic thoughts questionnaire-Believability (ATQB):** developed by Niemeyer et al. in 2002. It consists of 15 items, each with a 5-point Likert scale rating. Scores are summed across the 15 items to form an ATQB index ranging from 15 to 75. A higher score indicates a higher level of cognitive fusion with depressive thoughts. The internal consistency is good with Cronbach's alpha typically exceeding 0.80.

- **The Gratitude Questionnaire-Six Item Form (GQ-6):** is a six-item self-report questionnaire design to assess individual difference in the proneness to experience gratitude in daily life by McCullough, Emmons and Tsang (2002). In this questionnaire participant rank certain statements along a 7-point Likert scale from "1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= Slightly disagree, 4=Neutral, 5=Slightly agree, 6=Agree, 7=Strongly agree". Item 3 and 6 are reverse scored.

- **Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9):** is a self-reported screening tool that is designed to screen the presence and conditions of depression. It is a sub component of the larger Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ) which is framed on the DSM-IV diagnostic criteria. It is formulated by Drs Robert L spatter, Janet B.W Williams, Kurt Kroenke and others. It has 9 items scoring 0 to 27 based on the 4-point Likert scale and reliability of 0.89.

Procedure

First of all, the topic of research was approved from the institute. After this approval, permission was taken from authors of the scales and the use of these scales in the present study. After this, permission letters for the data collection were issued and signed from the supervisor and Director of the Institute. The formal permission has been guaranteed from different universities of the Lahore, to collect the data. Consent form was taken from the participants. The purpose of the research was mentioned to the participants briefly but in general. The participants would receive instructions on the questionnaire and they were notified that their confidentiality was observed. Those who participated were made aware of their ethical rights that they can exercise throughout the course of the research as in withdrawing themselves out of the research at

whenever they wished in the course of the time. The system will take average time of filling a questionnaire as 15 minutes. Data collected will be keyed in SPSS and analyzed based on hypothesis and analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical Guidance by APA provided for the research with human participants code of conduct was followed in research study. The considerations were as follows:

- Research proposal was approved from the Institute
- To initiate study, permission was taken from the authors whose psychological scales were intended to use in the current study.
- Participants were reassured about the confidentiality of their personal information, and results of the study.
- Participants were assured that their anonymity will be maintained.
- Participant was assured that is no potential form of any physical, social, or psychological harm in this research.
- Results will be reported and analyzed accurately and solely used for the academic purpose.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The collected data were first screened and coded using IBM SPSS Statistics to ensure accuracy, identify any missing values, and verify the assumptions required for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were generated to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants and the distribution of key study variables. To examine the associations between negative thinking, gratitude, and depression, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed, allowing for the identification of the direction and strength of linear relationships among these

psychological variables. Furthermore, linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the predictive value of negative thinking and gratitude on depression levels, thereby determining how well these variables could statistically explain variations in depressive symptoms. To explore gender-based differences in the key variables, an independent samples t-test was used, providing insight into whether male and female participants differed significantly in terms of negative thinking, gratitude, or depression. All analyses were performed at a 95% confidence level, and findings were interpreted in light of the study's objectives and existing literature.

Results

This study was designed to explore the relationship between relationship among negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. In this chapter, the statistical analyses were applied to analyze the test hypothesis. Descriptive statistics was applied to see the demographic characteristics of sample (N=200). A Pearson correlation was used to measure the relationship between relationship among negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. Independent sample T-test was applied to assess the gender differences in independent and dependent variables. Regression analysis was run to measure that what are the predictors of depression among adults.

On Demographic analysis of the sample the average age of participants was 23.54 years and SD= 3.29, thus implying a range of ages. The average number of siblings were 4 (SD = 1.80) and gender average was M= 1.75and SD=.437 (male =51 & female=149) respectively. The average birth order position was M=1.9 (SD = 7.78) as 1st born =68, middle=84, last born=46 and only child=2. the average Qualification=2.02(.709) Intermediate=48, Graduation= 100, master=52, similarly Family structure M=1.8, SDF(.389) with social status m= 27.4,SD= .62 among the sample.

Table 1

Descriptive characteristics of sample (N=200)

Variable	M(SD)	f
Age	23.54 (3.29)	200
Gender	1.75(.437)	
Male		51
Female		149

Variable	Male		Female		t (198)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
ATQ-B	35.98	23.26	33.19	10.13	1.55	.120	0.1
GQ-6	28.27	6.27	29.32	4.59	-1.26	.207	-0.1
PHQScale	20.67	5.33	18.84	5.32	2.09	.038	0.34
Number of siblings		4.00(1.81)					
Birth order		1.91(.778)					
1 st born					68		
Middle born					84		
Last born					46		
Only child					2		
Qualification		2.02(.709)					
Intermediate					48		
Graduation					100		
master					52		
Family structure		1.8(.389)					
Joint					37		
nuclear					163		
Social status		2.74(.620)					
Upper class					3		
Upper middle class					60		
Middle class					125		
Lower middle class					10		
Lower class					2		

Table 2

Independent sample T test

Descriptive Statistical and Result of Independent t test of mean difference of Gender (men and women) on Negative thinking, gratitude and depression in young adults (N=200).

Note= N=200, M =Mean, SD= Standard deviation. *p<.05

Table 2 shows that independent sample t test was run to analyze gender difference on (DV) Depression score between two groups (male and Female). The result shows that male (M=20.76, SD= 5.33) had significantly higher score than female (M=18.84, SD=5.33), $t(198) = 2.09, p = .038$. there is statistical difference exist in depression level among male and females at level $p < .05$. The small size

(Cohen's $d = 0.34$) suggested a modest difference in depression score between male and female.

It was hypothesized that there is likely to be a positive significant relationship between higher levels of repetitive negative thinking and greater depressive symptoms and Greater dispositional gratitude will be inversely correlated with depressive symptoms among adults. Then the following analysis shows in below.

Table 3

Pearson partial correlation

Showing relationship between negative thinking (ATQ-B) and depression (PHQ 9).

Variables	N	M	SD	1	2
ATQ-B	200	19.32	5.37	-	.698**
PHQ-9	200	33.91	11.05	.698**	-

Note = N= sample (N=200), M=mean, SD=standard deviation, $p < .01^{**}$.

The results revealed a strong positive relation between Negative thinking (IV) and depression (DV) with scores $r = .689, p < .01^{**}$. It suggested that higher level of negative thinking are associated with greater

depression severity. This correlation was statistically significant at the level of 0.01, indicating a statistically significant relationship between negative thinking (IV) and depression (DV).

Table 4

Pearson Partial Correlation

Showing relationship between negative thinking (ATQ-B) and depression (PHQ 9).

Variables	N	M	SD	1	2
GQ-6	200	33.91	11.05	-	-.203**
PHQ-9	200	19.32	5.37	-.203**	

Note= N= sample(N=200), M=mean, SD=standard deviation, $p < .01^{**}$.

The results revealed a strong positive relation between gratitude (IV) and depression (DV) with scores $r = -.203, p < .01^{**}$. It suggested that higher level of gratitude is associated with lower depression severity. This correlation was statistically significant at the level of 0.01, indicating a statistically significant relationship between gratitude (IV) and depression (DV).

repetitive negative thinking and greater depressive symptoms and Greater dispositional gratitude will be inversely correlated with depressive symptoms among adults.

So, hypothesis was supported that there is likely to be positive relationship between higher levels of

It was hypothesized that negative thinking in adults is likely to be significant predictor of depression in young adults. To find out the predicting effect of negative thinking, depression (N=200) regression analysis was run.

Multiple Simple Linear Regression

Table 5

Multiple linear regression analysis showing predicting effect of negative thinking and gratitude on Self-Compassion (N=200).

Variable	B	β	SE
ATQ-B	25.54		2.17
GQscale	-.214	-.203	.074
R^2	.041		

Note = ATQ-B= Automatic thought Questionnaire, GQ-6=gratitude questionnaire

Table 5 presents the results of a multiple linear regression analysis conducted to identify the predictors of depression among young adults. The overall regression model was found to be statistically significant, with an R^2 value of .041, indicating that the predictor variables accounted for 4.1% of the variance in depression, $F(1, 492) = 8.492, p < .001^*$. The standardized beta coefficient for gratitude in predicting depression was $\beta = -.203$, suggesting a significant negative relationship between gratitude and depression. This finding supports the

hypothesis that higher levels of gratitude are associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms. Moreover, the Gratitude Questionnaire (GQ) emerged as a significant negative predictor of depression ($\beta = -.23, p < .001$), reinforcing the role of gratitude as a psychological protective factor. The model also indicated that negative thinking significantly predicted lower levels of gratitude ($p < .001^*$), suggesting an inverse relationship between these two variables. These results support the hypothesis that negative thinking is positively associated with depression, and that gratitude serves

as a buffering factor against depressive symptoms among young adults.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore the relationship among Negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. In adults there is highlighted desire to be attached or have intense relation with someone and when they get lonely and are divide of any close proximity then they got agitated and touchy which may cause many behavioral changes in them such as gratitude or depressed feeling. It was hypothesized that there are likely to be gender differences in negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults.

It was hypothesized that there are likely to be gender differences in negative thinking, gratitude and depression among adults. In recent research Nguyen et al. (2025) investigated how poor executive function contributed to depression in college students and determined that negative thinking patterns and depressive symptoms were subject to demographic variables (such as gender), which indicated gender-based differences in the said domain. In their part, Liang et al. (2020) informed that the effect of gratitude on depression with the intermediate links of peace of mind and rumination did not differentiate between the sexes, which means that gender should be considered when examining mental functions. Higher rates of prevalence of depressive symptoms were reported in Pakistani undergraduate students (Khan et al., 2021), but gender difference was indicated as a moderating aspect of psychological vulnerability. In the world, depression in women was by about 50 percent when compared to depression in men, which confirmed the significance of gender in the expression of depression and associated cognitive parameters such as negative thinking and gratitude (Nguyen et al., 2025; Liang et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Terlizzi, 2020).

It was hypothesized that Higher levels of repetitive negative thinking will be positively correlated with greater depressive symptoms. Nguyen et al. (2025) study had proved that the presence of poor executive functioning among college students predisposes them to engaging in repetitive negative thoughts, which immediately correlates with the increased

depressive symptoms to develop a strong relationship between the two variables. Benedetti et al. (2022) also proved that the existence of negative thought pattern is a central characteristic of major depression and post-COVID depression as repetitive negative thoughts overlap and lead to prolonged depressive conditions. Akhtar et al. (2020) found a high level of depressive symptoms in university students in LMICs, including Pakistan, and the repetitive negative thinking has been indicated as a part of the cognitive factor. Lastly, Adil et al. (2021) established that negative automatic thoughts played a significant mediator role between parental competence and the presence of postpartum depression in Pakistani mothers depicting that greater negative thoughts increase the depression severity. (Nguyen et al., 2025; Benedetti et al., 2022; Akhtar et al., 2020; Adil et al., 2021).

It was also hypothesized that Negative thinking is significant predict of depression in adults. Benedetti et al. (2022) discovered that negative cognitive styles forecast depressive psychopathology in patients with post-COVID, where negative thinking as a major contributor to the development of depression was observed. In the same way, Nguyen et al. (2025) demonstrated that poor executive function, which evoked repetitive negative thinking, resulted directly in increased depressive symptoms in students during the pandemic. This predictive relationship is also supported by the discovery made by Irfan and Zulkefly (2022) to have a positive correlation between negative automatic thoughts and depressive symptoms in late adolescents in Pakistan. Furthermore, negative thinking was identified as a predictor of postpartum depression in Pakistani mothers, in particular, those who had cesarean delivery, and it was established that negative thinking predicted depression among Pakistani adult populations (adults and mothers) (Benedetti et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2025; Irfan & Zulkefly, 2022;

It was hypothesized that Greater dispositional gratitude will be inversely correlated with depressive symptoms. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that Iodice et al. (2021) performed a meta-analysis that reflects that there is a significant negative correlation between gratitude and depression in different populations. Liang and colleagues

identified that gratitude has a protective effect (Liang et al., 2020), as their findings revealed that it decreased depression through inner peace and limited rumination. Jans-Beken et al. (2020) showed that there was a significant improvement in the manifestations of depression and anxiety during gratitude interventions, and the duration of the effects continued up to a period of six months after the interventions. Also, Cregg and Cheavens (2021) revealed that gratitude and depression were inversely related in patients with chronic diseases, which confirmed the study of Iodice et al. (2021), Liang et al. (2020), Jans-Beken et al. (2020), and Cregg and Cheavens (2021).l., 2021).

To sum up, Repetitive negative thinking has been identified as a critical vulnerability factor in the field of cognition that is tightly connected to the high levels of depression, whereas gratefulness can be found as a key protective psychological force that is negatively correlated with depression levels among different populous and situations. Negative thinking and gratitude in relation to gender also affect how these negative issues show themselves and the intercession is required to be more subtle and gender-sensitive. The fact that the negative thinking predicts depression, and gratitude is the mitigating predictor of the same is consistent across the findings that informs the relevance of the constructs as a primary psychological means of prevention and treatment interventions. Nevertheless, Pakistani studies demonstrate that the generalization of evidence found in other parts around the world may not be reliable in implementing the intervention to fit the regional socio-culture. In sum, the intervention (at least in its hypothesis) with the emphasis on decreasing negative thought processes and increasing thanksgiving/gratitude expression has a great potential to facilitate the positive changes in mental health outcomes and decrease prevalence of depression, particularly among adults living in low- and middle-income countries such as Pakistan.

Limitations of the Study

The present study also has certain limitations and may affect the generalizability of its findings. The sample size was relatively small (N=200) and gender distribution was uneven with more female (F=149) and less male (M=51) which may have influenced the

results. Data was collected from single city Lahore limiting geographic and cultural representation of the sample. Due to short time period for data collection Correlational research design was used. However, a longitudinal approach is recommended for further studies to better understand changes over time. Additionally the focus of the study was Adults excluding other age group such as adolescents, middle aged and older aged, which should be explored in future research.

Implications

The present study makes a huge contribution to the existing literature by manifesting a significant relationship among negative thinking, gratitude, and depression in young adults.

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